

Proceedings A
Supplementary material

Maxwell's quasi-demon as a property of ideal gas in the equilibrium state

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Determining the approximate time to fill the hole channel.

Results of calculation of formula values (27)

$$\frac{n_1(\bar{z}, \bar{t})}{n} = 1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\sqrt{2}\bar{z}/\bar{t}} \exp\left(-\frac{u^2}{2}\right) du$$

are shown in Table 1.

The left column contains the non-dimensional coordinate \bar{z} , the top row contains the non-dimensional time \bar{t} .

For the calculations we assumed that the molecules move inside an L-length channel closed by a wall on one side. The molecules hit the wall elastically and move in the opposite direction. Therefore, the molecules passed along the channel from the entrance to the hole to the exit the distance equal 2L. Therefore, a condition is fulfilled for a non-dimensional coordinate $0 \leq \bar{z} \leq 2$. From the results obtained, it can be seen that in the channel cross-section defined by the non-dimensional coordinate $\bar{z} = 2$, with the non-dimensional time value $\bar{t} = 0.35$, the formula value (27) is zero. This means that there are no molecules. But there, at $\bar{t} = 0.4$, the value (27) is no longer equal to zero. Thus, the approximate non-dimensional filling time of the hole channel can be assumed to be $\bar{t}_0 = 0.35$.

The calculations were obtained using MS Excel.

Table 1. Results of calculation of formula values (27). The left column contains the non-dimensional coordinate \bar{z} , the top row contains the non-dimensional time \bar{t} .

	\bar{t}	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.35
\bar{z}						
0		0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
0.1		0.07865	0.23975	0.318676	0.361837	0.343084
0.2		0.002339	0.07865	0.172889	0.23975	0.20951
0.3		1.1E-05	0.016947	0.07865	0.144422	0.112721
0.4		7.71E-09	0.002339	0.029673	0.07865	0.053021
0.5		7.69E-13	0.000203	0.009211	0.03855	0.021676
0.6		0	1.1E-05	0.002339	0.016947	0.007668
0.7		0	3.72E-07	0.000484	0.006664	0.002339
0.8		0	7.71E-09	8.12E-05	0.002339	0.000614
0.9		0	9.83E-11	1.1E-05	0.000731	0.000138
1		0	7.69E-13	1.21E-06	0.000203	2.67E-05
1.1		0	3.66E-15	1.08E-07	5.03E-05	4.4E-06
1.2		0	0	7.71E-09	1.1E-05	6.21E-07
1.3		0	0	4.44E-10	2.15E-06	7.49E-08
1.4		0	0	2.06E-11	3.72E-07	7.71E-09

1.5		0	0	7.69E-13	5.69E-08	6.77E-10
1.6		0	0	2.31E-14	7.71E-09	5.07E-11
1.7		0	0	0	9.25E-10	3.23E-12
1.8		0	0	0	9.83E-11	1.76E-13
1.9		0	0	0	9.24E-12	8.1E-15
2		0	0	0	7.69E-13	0